

Spectral Studies of Some Substituted Chalcones-II

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Manuscript received 21 February 1972; revised 18 September 1972; accepted 4 December 1972

The UV and near visible spectra of twenty four chalcones have been recorded and the effect of various substituents in chalcone molecule has been correlated with the displacement ($\Delta\lambda$) and the intensity of electronic absorption. The hypothetical angle of deformation (\ominus) has been calculated for some ortho substituted (ring A) chalcones.

ABSORPTION spectra are reported for twenty-four α , β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds of the chalcone type with various substituents in ring A, viz., hydroxy, methoxy, methyl, nitro and chloro- in ethanol solution. The present paper summarizes the empirical regularities which were observed in the data on the ultraviolet and the near visible spectra of these compounds.

Experimental and Results

The chalcones required for the present work were prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of resacetophenone or ortho-hydroxyacetophenone with appropriate aromatic aldehydes, and were crystallised several times before use.

The ultraviolet and the near visible spectra were recorded in 95% ethanol, on the Beckman DB Spectrophotometer using 1.0 cm cell.

The values of λ_{max} and ϵ for the various substituted chalcones are summarized in table 1.

Discussion

Examination of Table 1 shows two common absorption bands; one in the ultraviolet (range 232-278 nm, marked +) and the other as K-band in the near visible (range : 303-383 nm, marked \neq). Comparison of the intensities between these two bands show that the shorter wave-length band is always weaker than the longer-wavelength band in the near-visible region (exception : compounds 1 and 14). The conclusion thus arrived at corroborate the findings of Jurd and Horowitz¹⁴.

Long-Wavelength Absorptions, Functional-Group Effects on the Intensity of Absorption : The shift of the K-band, $\Delta\lambda$, has been found to depend upon the nature and position of the substituent in ring (A) of the chalcone. The hyperchromic effect exhibited by the K-band seems to be related to the nature of the substituent (ring A). Thus the maximum

hyperchromic effect is shown by C_4 -methoxy substituent : ϵ , 32,680 (compound 10) compared to ϵ , 4,560 of the reference chalcone (compound 1). Table 2 shows the functional group effects on the intensity of K-band in the chalcone of series A & B respectively.

Thus it can be seen (Table 2) that the extent of intensification of the K-band depends upon the nature of the substituent in the order :

(cf. compounds 10, 7 and 4). The same sequence is observed to hold, whether the substituent is located in ortho, meta or para positions in ring A (series A, cf. compounds 10, 7, 4; 9, 6, 3 and 8, 5 and 2 respectively). For ring—A substituent, the intensification is more pronounced when the functional group is located in para position (cf. compounds 8, 9 and 10). This presumably arises due to the extended conjugation.

In the chalcones of series B the following generalization seems to hold in respect of substitution (ring A) on the hyperchromism of the K-band :

(cf. compounds 18, 15 and 20). Here again, one observes that this generalization holds true irrespective of the position of the substituent (cf. compounds 18, 15, 20; 19, 16, 21, 17 and 22). This trend parallels to that observed in series (A) namely, $\text{OH} > \text{Me}$.

For isomeric 2'-hydroxymethyl-chalcones and 2', 4'-dihydroxymethyl chalcones (cf. compounds 2, 3, 4; 15, 16, 17) the intensification varies with the position of the methyl substituent in ring A, in the order : para > meta > ortho. The same trend is observed with the isomeric 2',4'-dihydroxy chloro chalcones [cf. compounds 20, 21 and 22]. However, with isomeric 2',2'(3- and 4)-dihydroxy chalcones, 2,2',4' (and 3)-trihydroxy chalcones and 2'-hydroxy-2 (3- and 4)-methoxy chalcones [cf. compounds, 5, 6, 7; 18, 19; 8, 9 and 10], the sequence in which the intensification increases is given by para > ortho > meta.

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TABLE 1—ULTRAVIOLET AND NEAR VISIBLE SPECTRA OF SUBSTITUTED CHALCONES

Series (A) : $R_2 = H$; $R_1 = OH$

Compound No.	Reference	Substituents		UV		Near visible	
		X	Y	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ
1	1	H	H	207	19,840	332	5,810
				218	18,200		
				255+	6,300		
2	2	2-CH ₃	H	210	20,450	362(s) #	4,560
				224(s)	10,230		
				236+	6,490		
				277(s)	5,980		
				277(s)	5,980		
3	2	3-CH ₃	H	208	25,870	331	18,920
				234+	10,020		
				275(s)	9,220		
4	2	4-CH ₃	H	206	22,290	364(s) #	12,760
				222(s)	16,090		
				240+	7,720		
				292(s)	5,860		
				208	31,470		
5	3	2-OH	H	258+	15,280	368 #	16,810
				211	2,530		
6	4	3-OH	H	256+	8,170	352	14,110
				209	18,040		
7	5	4-OH	H	222(s)	11,380	370 #	26,430
				244	11,380		
				256(s)	9,990		
				276	6,370		
				209	28,220		
8	6	2-OCH ₃	H	252+	11,540	308	15,750
				274(s)	10,620		
				210	35,550		
9	7	3-OCH ₃	H	256+	14,850	362 #	20,100
				206	28,780		
10	4	4-OCH ₃	H	212(s)	21,980	345	20,810
				244+	20,210		
				276	14,560		
				210	19,840		
				218	17,300		
11	8	3-NO ₂	H	278+(s)	14,690	358 #	32,680
				212	29,950		
				244+	11,180		
12	4	2-OH	3-OCH ₃	270	14,460	306 #	19,300
				216	33,010		
				255+	9,420		
				287(s)	9,420		
				270	14,460		
13	4	2-OCH ₃	3-OCH ₃	216	33,010	380 #	27,570
				255+	9,420		

Series (B) : $R_2 = R_1 = OH$

14	9	H	H	207	29,480	358 #	10,130
				221	22,130		
				266+(s)	15,300		
15	10	2-CH ₃	H	275(s)	16,600	363 #	17,540
				206	35,720		
				236(s)	14,780		
				261+(s)	12,490		
16	10	3-CH ₃	H	207	28,200	357 #	18,480
				226(s)	10,240		
				264+(s)	4,730		
				283(s)	8,030		
17	10	4-CH ₃	H	209	21,090	360 #	24,200
				225(s)	12,720		
				258+	4,630		
18	11	2-OH	H	210	26,200	311	13,440
				254+	6,960		
19	12	3-OH	H	211	37,470	373 #	23,260
				256+	8,950		
				211	37,470		
						314	18,310
						360 #	20,910

TABLE 1—*Contd.* ULTRAVIOLET AND NEAR VISIBLE SPECTRA OF SUBSTITUTED CHALCONES

Compound No.	Reference	Substituents		UV		Near visible	
		X	Y	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ
20	8	2-Cl	H	210	26,340	352#	14,680
				234 ⁺ (s)	7,700		
				272(s)	5,020		
21	8	3-Cl	H	207	34,960	359#	17,090
				220(s)	23,610		
				232(s)	17,480		
				269 ⁺ (s)	16,100		
				298	21,140		
22	8	4-Cl	H	209	23,380	360#	18,440
				222	16,360		
				269 ⁺ (s)	7,420		
				208	27,830		
23	8	3-NO ₂	H	220(s)	13,580	303#	13,580
				255 ⁺ (s)	7,430		
				275	12,620		
				207	26,450		
				262 ⁺	6,570		
24	10	3-OCH ₃	4-OH	207	26,450	383#	27,290
				262 ⁺	6,570		

s = shoulder or inflection. + = shorter wavelength maxima. # = longer wavelength maxima.

Furthermore, the hyperchromic effect on the longer wavelength band is more pronounced in the case of chalcones (series A and B) carrying substituents like hydroxyl or methoxy than methyl in ring A (cf. compounds 5, 6, 7; 18, 19; 8, 9, 10 and 2, 3, 4; 15, 16, 17). This effect can be rationalized in term of the ease of electron availability, (which is proportional to the probability of electronic excitation (absorptivity, ϵ). The absorptivity, however, decreases relatively, when these substituents are situated at C₃-position on ring A. This effect arises, presumably due to lack of resonance contribution by the substituent in meta position. In this situation it appears that the substituent is capable of exerting only the inductive effect on the aromatic ring.

Examination of Table 2 further reveals that the magnitude of intensification with methyl or hydroxyl substitution (in ortho-, meta- or para-position) in series A is more than in series B. The introduction of C₄-hydroxyl (ring B) is apparently responsible for the observed change.

Effect of C₂-hydroxyl Substitution in Ring B on the Longer Wavelength Absorption: The introduction of ortho hydroxylic function in the benzoyl residue of an unsubstituted chalcone¹⁶ (λ_{max} 310 nm, ϵ , 27,000) produces a large bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda$,

+52 nm) and is accompanied by a considerable decrease in the intensity of K-band, viz., about one-sixth of the original value.

The large bathochromic shift can be accounted for as the combination of substituent effect due to hydroxylic function as well as due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The latter effect is also responsible for causing a bathochromic shift is shown by Dannenberg¹⁸ in the case of salicylic acid.

Effect of Substituents on the Longer Wavelength Maxima: Examination of Table 1 reveals the trend in the longer wavelength maxima and is a function of the substituent (nature) in the ring A. Thus, for example the maximum bathochromic shift, ($\Delta\lambda$, +18 nm compared to compound 1 taken as reference) was observed in the case of compound 12, due to the presence 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy substituents; and a blue shift ($\Delta\lambda$, -56 nm) arising due to the 3-nitro group (cf. compound 11). In the case of compound 12, referred to above, the displacement of the longer wavelength maxima ($\Delta\lambda$, +18 nm) cannot be equated with the algebraic sum of the value (+12 nm) of the two substituents. In order to explain this discrepancy it, therefore, seems reasonable to assume that the two substituents, viz., C₂-hydroxyl and C₃-methoxyl in ring A are exerting a mutual influence on each other. The hypsochromic effect brought

TABLE 2. INTENSIFICATION OF THE LONGER WAVELENGTH ABSORPTION MAXIMA BY SUBSTITUENTS

Series	Substituent X	Intensification factor	Substituent X	Intensification factor	Substituent X	Intensification factor
A	2-CH ₃	2.2	3-CH ₃	2.7	4-CH ₃	3.1
	2-OH	3.6	3-OH	3.0	4-OH	5.7
	2-OCH ₃	4.4	3-OCH ₃	3.8	4-OCH ₃	7.1
B	2-CH ₃	1.7	3-CH ₃	1.8	4-CH ₃	2.4
	2-OH	2.3	3-OH	2.0	4-OH	2.4*
	2-Cl	1.5	3-Cl	1.7	4-Cl	1.8

* expected value. Intensification factor = $\frac{\epsilon \text{ substituted chalcone}}{\epsilon \text{ reference chalcone}}$

about by the presence of C₃-nitro substituent (cf. compound 11) is in accord with the generalization put forward by Szamant and Basso¹³, viz., that an electron attracting group (nitro-group for example) on ring A causes a large blue shift. The C₃-nitro group cannot be involved directly in resonance. Similar results are observed in respect of series B. Thus maximum red shift ($\Delta\lambda$, +25 nm) occurs with the introduction of C₃-methoxy and C₄-hydroxyl substituents (ring A) in 2',4'-dihydroxychalcone; and a large hypsochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda$, -55 nm) due to C₃-nitro group (cf. compounds 23 and 14).

Substitution in ring A (methyl, methoxy, hydroxy, chloro or nitro) cause a hyperchromic effect on the K-band (vide supra), but substitution in ring B (hydroxyl function, cf. unsubstituted chalcone¹⁶, λ_{max} 310 nm; ϵ , 27,000 with compounds 1 and 14) produces a hypsochromic effect.

Effect of ortho Chloro Substitution in ring A on the Longer Wavelength Absorption: The chloro substituent in ortho position (series II) exerts a hypsochromic effect ($\Delta\lambda$, -6 nm), which is consistent with our earlier observations¹⁵. Similar results are obtained in the case of 2-chlorochalcone¹³ ($\Delta\lambda$, -19 nm).

In meta- and para positions, however, the chloro substituent produces a minor bathochromic shift accompanied by a hyperchromic effect on the longer wavelength absorption band. Similar findings are reported by two independent group of investigators^{13,16} and the hypsochromic effect is explained to be presumably, due to steric effect¹⁷ of the substituent. Alternatively, the observed hypsochromic effect may be explained if it is assumed that the C₂-chloro-substituent is operating inductively.

Calculation of Angle of Deformation Caused by ortho Substitution (Ring A) of Chalcones: We have also calculated the angle of deformation (θ) for the substituted chalcones carrying an ortho substituent, viz., methyl, hydroxy, methoxy and chloro-. The value of θ was obtained from the following expression¹⁸:

$$\cos^2 \theta = \frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_o}$$

where ϵ_a = extinction coefficient for the ortho substituted chalcone.

ϵ_o = extinction coefficient for the para substituted chalcone.

Thus the values of θ calculated for the various ortho substituted chalcones are 33°, 36°, 38°, 31° and 27° respectively [cf. compounds 2, 5, 8, 15 and 20]. These values are in good agreement with those reported by Wheeler, Gore, Santiago and Baez¹⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. U. C. Agarwala for his helpful comments and to Mr. A. H. Siddiqui for recording the spectra and to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (India) for the award of junior research fellowship to one of them (RKS).

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